

The Lotus: a curious case of Bengali Insignia

Abstract

This article is submitted as a research note identifying a previously unrecognised royal emblem of the Bengal Sultanate, through an analysis of a crest found on royal *loggia* inside of the Adina Mosque. The crest's placement at the apex of the *mihrab*, its use of the lotus symbolism and alignment with numismatic symbolism and Islamicate seals demonstrate that it functioned as a formal institutional emblem of sovereignty of the Bengal Sultanate.

Figure 1: A generic Bengal Sultanate era lotus

In the architecture and the art of the Bengal Sultanate, the lotus served as a crucial ornamental bridge between local pre-Islamic and newly introduced political Islamic traditions. Found primarily on terracotta relief and stone carvings, (Figure 1) the lotus motif was removed from its distinct Hindu and Buddhist theological affiliations while retaining its indigenous symbolism. Found on mosques, temples, *darwazas* (gates), tombs of nobles and Sultans, imperial courts, inscriptions and coins, it was the foremost of the emblems of the Bengal Sultanate. While used predominantly for decorative purposes, it was integrated into the Royal Insignia of the Bengal Sultanate and the Bengali Sultans. Under these Bengali Sultans new variations of the lotus blossomed such as the large wheel.¹ Another leading variant seen in Royal Insignia was the Islamicate *shamsa* variation.

Despite the ubiquity of the lotus motif in the architecture of the Bengal Sultanate, its function as a formal emblem has not been systematically examined. Because of its prominence in the architecture of Bengal, scholars and researchers have dismissed it as a purely decorative device. However a critical re-examination of the specific crest in the Adina mosque and the lotus found in other official settings challenges this view. The following sections provide an analysis of this symbol.

Figure 2: The royal loggia found in Adina Mosque, containing the imperial achievement alias achievement of the state. The achievement is composed of a highly stylised lotus crest with chinoiserie flanking it on both sides

The usage of the lotus in official settings and Royal Insignia is relatively well documented in comparison to other sultanate era regalia, such as the lion. One example of this is its presence in imperial courts² like in Kusumba Mosque and Adina Mosque. These mosques were more than just places of worship, they were symbols of the sovereignty of Bengal. They doubled as imperial courts where the Sultan would sit on a throne specially prepared for him called the *Badshah-ka-Takht*, and deliver to a public audience.³ These places of royal authority were plentiful in their usage of the lotus, and it can even be seen on the throne of the Sultan. The placement of the lotus

emblems on the Sultan's throne could not have been a mere decorative practice but an intentional act with purpose. This, along with the employment of the lotus on coins and inscriptions leads me to say that it was not just peripheral ornamentation but also a component of Royal Insignia.

The interpretation of the lotus as also being part of the Royal Insignia of the Bengal Sultanate is supported by its prominence on the coinage of Bengal and also a curious crest found in Adina Mosque. The Adina Mosque was constructed by Sultan Sikander Shah in the 14th century. It represents the clearest articulation of imperial architectural language in sultanate Bengal. Built on an unprecedented scale, the mosque remains as the largest mosque in the Indian

1 George, *Heritage of Bengal*, 228-229.

2 No surviving example of an imperial court exists for the Bengal Sultanate. The only imperial courts which survive are imperial mosques which doubled as imperial courts.

3 Doza, "Badshah-ka Takht".

Subcontinent.⁴ The Mosque, constructed to commemorate Sikander's victory against Delhi,⁵ served as a political symbol and was not merely congregational, demonstrating a manifestation of Bengali independence after the Ekdala Wars. Looking further into the Adina Mosque, on the southern *mihrab*, there is a royal *loggia* (Figure 2).⁶ It contains a central crest which is flanked by chinoiserie including Chinese lotuses on both its sides.⁷ The crest however, is of particular interest as it contains a highly stylised lotus including an Islamicate *shamsa* variant in its centre (Figure 3). This crest is undoubtedly the imperial achievement *alias* achievement of the state or symbol of the government of the Bengal Sultanate, at least during the reign of Sikander Shah.

Figure 3: The Lotus found on the Royal arms of Bengal and its similarities to contemporary coinage. Left: Achievement impression, Right: Coin of Sikander Shah © reaz613@gmail.com (CC BY-SA)

The achievement is located in perhaps the single most symbolic place in the entirety of the mosque, the top of the *mihrab* creating a visual axis of power. The placement of anything regardless of whether it was insignia, on top of the *mihrab*, could not have been done so arbitrarily. Such a mosque would have been built with tremendous care that features like this would have been positioned with purposeful intent. Considering this, the crest could not have been a decorative device but a representation of imperial authority on the grounds that Adina Mosque was an imperial Mosque and an icon of Bengali independence in light of Delhi hegemony and political superiority. It would be unreasonable to assume otherwise given the status of the mosque as a symbol of Bengali sovereignty and the circumstances surrounding its construction.

(1352-1538 CE). It was an inter-dynastic emblem suggesting a Bengali state identity transcending ruling families. Looking closely at Figure 3, we can record the 8-sided lotus on both the achievement and many Bengali coins including a coin of the contemporaneous Sikander Shah. The Islamicate *shamsa* found in the centre of the achievement is also a common feature of Bengali coins highlighting the hybridity of local and Islamic cultural iconography.

Furthermore, the lotus imagery used on the achievement shares symbolic vocabulary to lotus insignia found on coins. The lotus insignia is found on a multitude of coins of the Sultans from the *Shahi* era

Crucially, an important point to note is that while the lotus on the coins have similar core elements to the achievement such as the eight-pointed structure and shamsa style motifs suggesting an intentional continuity of symbolic conventions, it does not follow that the exact variations and designs of the lotus used on the coins, were used on the achievement. This is likely due to the difficulty in reproducing such a highly stylised achievement onto a simple coin. This would explain the actions of the Sultans in resorting to using these lesser or simplified versions of the full royal arms as it would have proved more functional, similar to the lesser coat of arms tradition in Europe (Figure 4). This idea is corroborated by analysing the lotus on the coins themselves. Many coins have an interesting feature where the lotus looks truncated or part of a larger design. The points of the lotus extend outward, seemingly continuing the design beyond the central circular motif of the coin suggesting these numismatic strikes were abbreviated versions of the more expansive royal arms (Figure 5). If this is the case, which it seems to be, then the lotuses found on Bengali coins are a lesser or simplified form of the full royal arms found in the Adina Mosque.

Figure 4: Examples of lesser Royal arms found on coins of Bengali Sultans featuring the lotus

Turning our attention back to the achievement, we find that it exhibits striking similarities to many Islamic seals. The circular format, centralised geometry and organisation of symbolism of the achievement are all common features on Islamic seals. While no known seals of Bengali Sultans are known to have survived, they would have also used seals in authentication and administrative purposes. The possibility of an adaptation of a seal like form onto portable and architectural insignia like the royal *loggia* further supports this identification.

Figure 5: Truncated versions of the imperial achievement on Bengali coins

4 Eaton, *Rise of Islam*, 42.

5 Bain, Pritam and Biswas, "Gaur and Pandua", 56.

6 Flood, "Before the Mughals", 19.

7 Ibid.

Ultimately, the architectural, numismatic and iconographic evidence demonstrates that the lotus in the Bengal Sultanate operated as more than a decorative remnant of pre-Islamic culture. Rather, it was deliberately repurposed into an emblem of sovereignty and imperial authority. The strategic placements within the spaces of power such as the *Badshah-ka-Takht*, coinage, inscriptions, darwazas and the apex of the *mihrab* in Adina Mosque indicates conscious state use rather than adorning coincidence. The Adina achievement, in particular, illustrates a crystallisation of this emblematic language, combining indigenous lotus forms with Islamicate cultural traditions like the shamsa motifs and seal-like composition articulating royal power through its usage as the royal arms.

Figure 6: The imperial achievement alias achievement of the state with the worn impressions regularised

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